

UNDERSTANDING THE SOCIAL PREFERENCES FOR THE CONSERVATION OF TRADITIONAL PIG BREEDS: THE CASE OF THE *PORC NEGRE MALLORQUÍ*

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Abstract

Among the profound changes that agriculture has experienced in the last 50 years, the genetic erosion of domesticated animals arises as one of them. Approximately 40% of local breeds in Europe are under risk of extinction.

The Majorcan porc negre is a local pig breed and one of the key elements of the traditional rural economy of the central region of the Majorca Island. It is a very rustic breed, highly adapted to its environment. Its meat is the main ingredient of the Majorcan sobrassada, a spreadable dry cured sausage. However, the porc negre reduced productivity compared to intensive breeds and the abandonment of rural activities have led to the progressive decline of its population.

This study intends to assess the social preferences for the conservation of the *porc negre mallorquí*, its management system and traditional products. For this purpose a choice experiment survey was conducted with a representative sample of 400 respondents in the island of Majorca. Our survey addressed the conservation of the breed, but also other aspects related to its management, the associated landscape and meat-based products.

Our preliminary results show that a high heterogeneity exists in social preferences, with an overall trend indicating that people are willing to secure the breed population levels and some key elements of the management system related to tree crop diversity. Our outcomes may be of help in the design of policy measures to support the breed and its landscape.

Keywords: choice experiment, agrarian diversity, landscape, traditional products

1. Introduction

Among the profound changes that agriculture has experienced in the last 50 years, the genetic erosion of domesticated animals arises as one of them. Approximately 40% of local breeds in Europe are under risk of extinction (FAO, 2000a). The economic values that these breeds and their management systems generate are not captured in the market place, generating a distortion where the incentives are against genetic resources conservation and in favor of the economic activities that erode such resources (Pearce and Moran, 1994).

The Majorcan porc negre is a local pig breed and one of the key elements of the traditional rural economy of the central region of the Majorca Island. It is a very rustic breed, highly adapted to its environment and closely linked to the agroforestry polycultures (fig trees, helm oaks, almond trees and carob trees) and to the mosaic landscape of the island. Its meat is the main ingredient of the Majorcan sobrassada, a spreadable dry cured sausage. However, the porc negre reduced productivity compared to intensive breeds and the abandonment of rural activities have led to the progressive decline of its population and the displacement of these rural practices by other more profitable economic activities.

This study intends to estimate the social preferences and values for the public good dimensions of the porc negre and its management system, namely addressing values related to the breed existence, its welfare and the cultural values represented by the rearing systems, landscape maintenance (conveying recreational values) and the meat products associated to the breed.

2. Methods

A choice experiment (CE) survey was conducted in the island of Majorca. The survey was addressed to a sample of 400 respondents, with equal weights between rural and urban dwellers. CE is rooted on the Lancasterian theory of value (Lancaster 1966) and the random utility theory (Mc Fadden, 1973).

We adopted a random parameter logit (RPL) specification. RPL models are flexible estimation methods that are being increasingly employed to model people's preferences within the random utility framework (Train, 2009). All attribute parameters related to porc negre management system were effects coded, assumed to be random and following a normal distribution. The cost attribute parameter was assumed to be fixed as we wished to restrict it to be non-positive for all individuals. A maximum likelihood estimation of the model parameters was conducted using simulation with 500 Halton draws.

The attributes and their levels considered in this study can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. *Attributes and levels*

Attribute	Levels	Coding names in model estimation
Existence of the breed in the future	<200 sows* Risk of extinction HIGH	
	200-1000 sows Risk of extinction MEDIUM	MED risk
	> 1000 sows Risk of extinction LOW	LOW risk
Type of management	Most of the time outdoors*	
	50% outdoors,50% indoors	OUT-IN
	Most of the time indoors	IN
Diversity of tree species	Most of the area with 1 species * LOW variety of tree species	
	Most of the area with 2 species MEDIUM variety of tree species	TSP2
	Most of the area with 3 species HIGH variety of tree species	TSP3
Type of landscape	LOW heterogeneity*	
	MEDIUM heterogeneity	MED_land
	HIGH heterogeneity	HIGH_land
Product variety	LOW variety*	
	MEDIUM variety	MED_prod
	HIGH variety	HIGH_prod
COST	10,20,30,40,50,60	

* Status quo

3. Results and discussion

A total of 144 respondents out of 400 (36% of the sample) were identified as protesters, through a close-ended follow-up question and removed from ulterior model estimation. Table 2 shows the results obtained.

Respondents on average show significant and positive preferences for reducing the risk of extinction of the breed and improve its population numbers. A strong rejection is found for indoor breeding systems compared the traditional outdoor one. Further exploration of the results obtained in the attitudinal questions is needed; however, participants in focus groups stated that their main reason to prefer outdoor breeding systems is the better meat quality. Respondents also show a positive and significant preference for the three species levels for the tree crops, indicating preference for improving the status of the tree crops and their diversity. Finally respondents also show a negative preference for the landscape showing medium heterogeneity compared to the base low heterogeneous level. The highly significant and negative sign of the ASC shows that respondents on average and ceteris paribus, would prefer to move away from the status quo option.

Most attributes show significant and notable standard deviations of parameter distributions, indicating a high heterogeneity, beyond average estimates, of respondents' preferences. Furthermore, in some cases the high values of these standard deviations may suggest that further investigation of modelling approaches that better accommodate respondents' heterogeneity, may be needed, considering accounting for respondents' utility in a discrete manner.

VARIABLES	RPL		Adj ^a
	Coefficients	Std. dev. of param. Distrib.	
MED risk	0.044 (0.127)	0.695 (0.184)***	0.657
LOW risk	0.569 (0.230)**	2.665 (0.276)***	1.182**
OUT-IN	0.359 (0.187)*	0.285 (0.497)	-0.641*
IN	-1.359 (0.277)***	1.688 (0.215)***	-2.359***
TSP2	0.055 (0.175)	0.490 (0.227)**	0.745
TSP3	0.635 (0.187)***	0.979 (0.211)***	1.325***
MED_land	-0.420 (0.170)**	0.678 (0.289)**	-1.092**
HIGH_land	-0.252 (0.218)	0.526 (0.485)	-0.924
MED_prod	-0.031 (0.156)	0.781 (0.231)***	-0.146
HIGH_prod	-0.084 (0.159)	0.930 (0.244)***	-0.199
ASC	-1.361(0.401)***	Fixed	
COST	-0.029 (0.007)***	Fixed	
N observations	256		
Loglikelihood	-1173.25		
McFadden pseudo-R2	0.30		

*** p < 0.01 ** p < 0.05 *p < 0.10

^a Adjusted marginal utility gains from the base level situation for the effects-coded attributes

4. Conclusions

This work presents preliminary results of a valuation survey to account for the social preferences for the porc negro traditional pig breed and its management system which show public good features that are not remunerated by the market. Initial estimates show a strong preference for improving the conservation status of its population and for maintaining the traditional outdoor breeding system.

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Bibliography

FAO, 2000. World Watch List for Domestic Animal Diversity. Rome, Italy.

Lancaster, K.J., 1966. A new approach to consumer theory. *J. Polit. Econ.* 74, 132–157.

McFadden, D., 1974. Conditional logit analysis of qualitative choice behavior. En: Zarembka, I. (Ed.), *Frontiers in Econometrics*. Academic Press, New York, pp.105–142.

Pearce, D., Moran, D., 1994. *The Economic Value of Biodiversity*. Earthscan, London, UK.

Train, K., 2009. *Discrete Choice Methods With Simulation*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.